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PRESILIENT

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in Ecuador.

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Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project to investigate the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

This Ecuador-focused report employs qualitative and desk-based methods, including a literature review, policy and media analysis, and grey literature, to explore emerging socio-economic and political-economic trends within the country's informal and primary sectors. Unlike other reports that rely heavily on large-scale quantitative data or automated keyword mapping, this study offers an in-depth interpretive analysis grounded in a contextual understanding of Ecuador's rural and urban dynamics. The research is driven by insights from international development and criminological studies, which inform a critical perspective on informality, governance, and the complex socio-political factors shaping economic practices.

Findings reveal the structural duality of Ecuador's economy, where the rural and agricultural sectors, largely informal and community-based, proved more resilient during the pandemic than urban services such as tourism, transport, and retail, which were severely impacted. Informal labour remains widespread, especially in agriculture, and disproportionately affects women and Indigenous populations. In response to the crisis, grassroots innovations emerged, including digital delivery systems, solidarity networks, and urban agriculture. However, structural inequalities, limited infrastructure, and socio-political exclusion continue to constrain broader inclusion. The analysis highlights the importance of Indigenous and community-based practices as resilience strategies and advocates for inclusive policies that respect cultural autonomy and diverse livelihoods.

Keywords

Informality; Informal Economy; Illicit trade; Corruption; Bribery; Embezzlement; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Sustainable development; Ethics; Reliability; Agri-food sector ; Third-party certifications; Poverty; Rural communities; Cooperatives; Farmers; Inspectors; Labels

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Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Ecuadorian country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report adopts a qualitative, anthropologically informed approach, focusing on sectoral fluctuations and how local actors interpret, resist, or creatively adapt to structural pressures.

In this Ecuadorian case, no large-scale statistical dataset or automated bibliometric analysis was used. Instead, the methodological approach focused on:

- A thematic review of literature, reports, and critical essays related to informality, livelihoods, and resilience in Ecuador.
- Analysis of grey literature, policy documents, and national and international development discourse.
- A comparative analysis of media narratives and regional studies, incorporating both mainstream and independent sources that tend to capture grassroots voices and offer perspectives less shaped by formal institutional interests.
- Engagement with research on agricultural and rural economies, emphasising Indigenous and community-based practices within development frameworks.

This interpretive and grounded approach aligns with PRESILIENT's epistemological stance, which views informality in Ecuador not as a mere statistical issue but as a vital space of knowledge, agency, and innovation. The report highlights the political and ethical dimensions of economic practices, especially in the informal agricultural and community-based sectors, where informality is closely linked to broader struggles for cultural autonomy, social dignity, and environmental sustainability. Within this framework, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of Ecuador's post-pandemic socio-economic dynamics. They will support subsequent project phases, including expert Delphi surveys and detailed case studies. Notably, the analysis offers policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant narratives around formalisation and promoting alternative economic models grounded in the lived realities of marginalised communities.

Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the standard research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also employed a

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structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. Data collection relied on pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. Following shared methodological guidelines, the Ecuador study drew on a structured corpus of 150 sources—50 academic publications, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents—selected through targeted searches, curated for relevance, and critically analysed using the researcher’s contextual knowledge of Ecuador’s socio-economic realities. The process involved iterative keyword refinement, source triangulation, and inclusion of both mainstream and independent media to capture diverse, often underrepresented grassroots perspectives. Each step, from keyword selection to report drafting, is transparently documented to ensure methodological rigour. Grounded in qualitative synthesis and deep insight into Ecuador’s primary sector and social dynamics, the report is informed by international development and criminological frameworks, emphasising the complex governance and socio-political factors shaping informality. This approach produces a robust analysis that reflects local realities and contributes to the broader comparative project.

Informal Economies in Ecuador: Socioeconomic Context

Ecuador is classified as a developing economy with a heavy reliance on commodities, particularly oil and agricultural products. Agriculture plays a significant role in the country’s GDP and employment, with key exports including bananas, cocoa, and coffee. Informal employment accounts for approximately 62% of the workforce, with more than half of these informal workers employed in the agricultural sector. Informality is more prevalent in rural areas than in urban centres, often associated with lower wages and a higher proportion of women in comparison to the formal sector. Ecuadorian society is composed of a diverse mix of communities, with Indigenous peoples representing a substantial share of the population, close to 40%, and 14 officially recognised Indigenous nationalities totalling over one million people. Minority groups are disproportionately affected by poverty, and ethnic segregation remains a persistent feature of the national labour market.

Regional and Global Comparison

Ecuador’s socio-economic profile reflects broader trends in Latin America, showing relatively strong performance in areas such as economic growth, sustainable development, and labour market participation. At the same time, its engagement with topics such as gender equality, care work, and the informal economy, particularly street vending, remains limited, reflecting the ongoing structural challenges throughout the region. Compared to some African and Asian countries, Ecuador tends to place less emphasis on sectors such as public health, social marginalisation, waste management, and the environmental and social impacts of tourism. These patterns suggest a policy focus primarily oriented toward macroeconomic stability, infrastructure, and poverty alleviation. At the same time, areas related to social equity, environmental services, and third-sector governance receive comparatively less attention.

Emerging Trends and Feedback

During the pandemic, innovative product delivery methods emerged, including the use of platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook, as well as home deliveries via personal vehicles or support from family and neighbours. Non-bank correspondents also resurged, driven by fear of visiting traditional banks. Credit unions gradually resumed lending and deposit-taking, supported by

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access to secondary financing that enabled them to assist rural and marginalised urban areas. Micro-entrepreneurs and social economy organisations adapted quickly, diversifying or shifting activities in response to the crisis. Private companies joined food donation and distribution efforts alongside municipalities, the Quito Food Bank, and humanitarian groups. Social movements facilitated direct sales from rural producers to urban households through weekly deliveries, easing mobility constraints. Urban agriculture became a key livelihood strategy for vulnerable families and poor neighbourhoods, demonstrating its role in resilience.

Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (including Ecuador). It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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References

Academic literature

1. Acevedo, I., Castellani, F., Lotti, G., & Székely, M. (2021). Informalidad en los tiempos del COVID-19 en América Latina: Implicaciones y opciones de amortiguamiento. Inter-American Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0003220>
2. Atal, J. P., Ñopo, H. R., & Winder, N. (2009). New Century, Old Disparities: Gender and Ethnic Wage Gaps in Latin America. IDB Publications. (Central America). Retrieved from <https://publications.iadb.org/en/publication/new-century-old-disparities-gender-and-ethnic-wage-gaps-latin-america>
3. Barbier, E. B. (2012). Corruption, Poverty and Tropical Land Use. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*, 31(4–5), 319–339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10549811.2011.588455>
4. Botello Peñalosa, H. A. B., & Guerrero Rincón, I. (2022). Informal Economy and Income Distribution in Ecuador During the COVID-19 Pandemic*. *Revista Facultad de Ciencias Económicas: Investigación y Reflexión*, 30 (1)(1), 11–28. <https://doi.org/10.18359/rfce.5206>
5. Canelas, C. (2019). Informality and poverty in Ecuador. *Small Business Economics*, 53(4), 1097–1115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-0102-9>
6. De Ferranti, D., Perry, G. E., Lederman, D., & Maloney, W. E. (2002). From Natural Resources to the Knowledge Economy: Trade and Job Quality. <https://doi.org/10.1596/0-8213-5009-9>
7. De Janvry, A., & Sadoulet, E. (2000). Rural poverty in Latin America Determinants and exit paths. *Food Policy*, 25, 389–409.
8. Friedman, E., Johnson, S., Kaufmann, D., & Zoido-Lobaton, P. (2000). Dodging the grabbing hand: The determinants of unofficial activity in 69 countries. *Journal of Public Economics*.
9. Friedmann, H., & McMichael, P. (2008). 'Agriculture and the State System: The Rise and Decline of National Agriculture'. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 29, 93–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9523.1989.tb00360.x>
10. Gërkhani, K. (2004). The Informal Sector in Developed and Less Developed Countries: A Literature Survey. *Public Choice*, 120(3), 267–300. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:PUCH.0000044287.88147.5e>
11. Hann, C., & Hart, K. (n.d.). *Market and Society: The Great Transformation Today*.
12. Weller, J. (2020). La pandemia del COVID-19 y su efecto en las tendencias de los mercados laborales. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/11362/45759>
13. Hart, K. (2006). Bureaucratic form and the informal economy. In B. Guha-Khasnobis, R. Kanbur, & E. Ostrom (Eds.), *Linking the Formal and Informal Economy: Concepts and Policies* (p. 0). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0199204764.003.0002>
14. Sumba-Bustamante, R. Y., Saltos-Ruiz, G. R., Rodríguez-Suarez, C. A., & Tumbaco-Santiana, Z. L. (2020). El desempleo en el ecuador: Causas y consecuencias. *Polo del Conocimiento*, 5(10), 774–797. <https://doi.org/10.23857/pc.v5i10.1851>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

15. Desfrancois, P., & Mayorga, T. (2022). La corrupción en el Ecuador: Un análisis económico. *Revista Colombiana de Ciencias Administrativas*, 4(2), 8–25. <https://doi.org/10.52948/rcca.v4i2.614>
16. Kovács, B., Morris, J., Polese, A., & Imami, D. (2017). Looking at the ‘sharing’ economies concept through the prism of informality. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 10(2), 365–378. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cjres/rsw046>
17. Vera-Ruiz, D. O., Tumbaco-Chilan, R. Y., & Concha-Ramirez, J. A. (2021). El impacto económico causado por el covid-19 en las empresas ecuatorianas del sector comercial. *Polo del Conocimiento*, 6(4), 941–955. <https://doi.org/10.23857/pc.v6i4.2619>
18. La Porta, R., & Shleifer, A. (2014). Informality and Development. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(3), 109–126. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.28.3.109>
19. Lewis, W. A. (1954). Economic Development with Unlimited Supplies of Labour. *The Manchester School*, 22(2), 139–191. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9957.1954.tb00021.x>
20. Loayza, N., Servén, L., & Sugawara, N. (2009). Informality in Latin America and the Caribbean. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1372965>
21. Vaquero García, A. (2020). Nuevos retos laborales ante la digitalización: Un análisis desde la perspectiva económica. *Temas laborales: Revista andaluza de trabajo y bienestar social*, (151), 311–326.
22. Middleton, A. (2019). The Informal Sector in Ecuador: Artisans, Entrepreneurs and Precarious Family Firms. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429201097>
23. Cantos, M. A. B., Quimis, S. J. G., & Laz, P. S. L. (2022). Impacto económico de la pandemia por el COVID 19 en las comercializadores y productoras de calzado en el cantón Portoviejo. *RECIMUNDO*, 6(suppl 1), 71–81. [https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/6.\(suppl1\).junio.2022.71-81](https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/6.(suppl1).junio.2022.71-81)
24. Schneider, F., & Buehn, A. (2018). Shadow Economy: Estimation Methods, Problems, Results and Open questions. *Open Economics*, 1(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1515/openec-2017-0001>
25. Vivares, E., & Salgado, R. (2021). From Latin American International political economy to Latin American global political economy. *Estudios Internacionais*, 9(2), 7–33. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.5752/P.2317-773X.2021v9n2p7-33>
26. Cobeña, G. V. S. (2021). COVID-19 y mercado laboral ecuatoriano: Impacto, esperanzas y oportunidades. *RECIMUNDO*, 5(1 (Suple)), 60–74. [https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/5.\(Suple1\).oct.2021.60-74](https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/5.(Suple1).oct.2021.60-74)
27. Webb, J. W., Tihanyi, L., Ireland, R. D., & Sirmon, D. G. (2009). You Say Illegal, I Say Legitimate: Entrepreneurship in the Informal Economy. *Academy of Management Review*, 34(3), 492–510. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2009.40632826>
28. Williams, C., & Schneider, F. (2013). The Shadow Economy. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1324.1286>
29. Abanto Carrión, E. M., Reátegui Guerra, R., Aco Miranda, O. M., & Medina Sotelo, C. G. (2021). La economía informal en tiempos de pandemia: Una crisis anunciada. *UCV-Scientia*.

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

30. Calvo, S., Syrett, S., & Morales, A. (2020). The political institutionalization of the social economy in Ecuador: Indigeneity and institutional logics. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 38(2), 269–289. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399654419857719>
31. Canelas, C. (2019). Informality and poverty in Ecuador. *Small Business Economics*, 53(4), 1097–1115. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-0102-9>
32. Weller, J., Gómez Contreras, M., Martín Caballero, A., & Ravest Tropa, J. (2020). El impacto de la crisis sanitaria del COVID-19 en los mercados laborales latinoamericanos. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/11362/45864>
33. Ricaurte-Quijano, C., & Baquerizo, S. E. (2017). Asociación, auto organización y agencia: Características del trabajo ambulante en cuatro playas de la costa ecuatoriana. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales (Ve)*, XXIII(4), 65–80.
34. Marchetti, S., & Cherubini, D. (2019). «Domestic work is work»: But for whom? Tensions around labour rights and the valorisation of reproductive labour in Ecuador and Colombia. *Rassegna Italiana Di Sociologia*, 60(4), 721–747. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1423/96113>
35. Ruesga, S., Perez, L., & Delgado, J. (2020). Sector informal en Ecuador: Perspectiva desde el escenario econométrico. Vol. 41(Nº 14), 17.
36. Rivera-Rhon, R., & Bravo-Grijalva, C. (2020). Crimen organizado y cadenas de valor: El ascenso estratégico del Ecuador en la economía del narcotráfico. URVIO. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios de Seguridad*, (28), 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.17141/urvio.28.2020.4410>
37. Fajardo-Ronquillo, V. P. (2020). Condiciones del empleo formal e informal en Ecuador. *Dominio de las Ciencias*, 6(2), 279–294. <https://doi.org/10.23857/dc.v6i2.1168>
38. Vega Núñez, A. P. (2018). Analysis of formal-informal transitions in the Ecuadorian labour market. *CEPAL Review*, 2017(123), 78–95. <https://doi.org/10.18356/5f68db3e-en>
39. Bravo, K. A. (2001). Bandido's. Una biografía indiscreta del subdesarrollo ecuatoriano. Retrieved from <https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/111477-opac>
40. Rivera-Rhon, R., & Bravo-Grijalva, C. (2020). Crimen organizado y cadenas de valor: El ascenso estratégico del Ecuador en la economía del narcotráfico. URVIO. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios de Seguridad*, (28), 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.17141/urvio.28.2020.4410>
41. Sánchez, C. P., & Mozo, A. M. G. (2009). Teletrabajo y vida cotidiana: Ventajas y dificultades para la conciliación de la vida laboral, personal y familiar. *Athenea Digital. Revista de pensamiento e investigación social*, 57–79. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/athenead/v0n15.597>
42. Jumbo Ordóñez, D. P., Campuzano Vásquez, J. A., Vega Jaramillo, F. Y., Luna Romero, Á. E., Jumbo Ordóñez, D. P., Campuzano Vásquez, J. A., ... Luna Romero, Á. E. (2020). Crisis económicas y covid-19 en Ecuador: Impacto en las exportaciones. *Revista Universidad y Sociedad*, 12(6), 103–110.
43. Treisman, D. (2000). The causes of corruption: A cross-national study. *Journal of Public Economics*, 76(3), 399–457. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2727\(99\)00092-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2727(99)00092-4)

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

44. Alcoser, R., & Alicia, A. (2018, December 17). Informality and labor reforms in Ecuador in the decade 2007-2017: Before and after? Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Informality-and-labor-reforms-in-Ecuador-in-the-%3A-Alcoser-Alicia/f914a1a7946d325f1aa4af0c3861c796a3ce06e2>
45. Carranco Paredes, S. F. (2018). The informal Economy in Ecuador. *INNOVA Research Journal*, 3(9), 44–52.
46. Núñez, J. L. B. (2021). El efecto del teletrabajo en el empleo en Ecuador durante la crisis sanitaria 2019-2020. *Sociedad & Tecnología*, 4(2), 223–234. <https://doi.org/10.51247/st.v4i2.106>
47. Chávez, M. M., Chávez, L. M., Morales, M. M., & Haro, D. L. (2023). La informalidad en el Ecuador: Una medición del tamaño del sector informal desde la perspectiva de la desigualdad. *Cuestiones Económicas*, 33(2), 21. <https://doi.org/10.47550/https://doi.org/10.47550/RCE/33.2.6>
48. Mahé, C., Zanoni, W., & Oliveri, M. L. (2022). Womens Informal Labor Market Participation in Ecuador. IDB Publications. (Ecuador). <https://doi.org/10.18235/0004646>
49. Fernández, G. M. Q., Nina, D. A., Villa, M. V. V., & Flores, R. V. (2020). Comercio informal en ciudades intermedias del Ecuador: Efectos socioeconómicos y tributarios. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales (Ve)*, XXVI(3), 207–230.
50. King, K., Samaniego, P., & Carranza, C. (2021). Facing covid-19 in Ecuador: A blueprint for monetary policy and food sovereignty. *Revue de La Régulation*, 29. <https://doi.org/10.4000/regulation.18524>

Press Articles

1. Astudillo, E. (2023, May 2). El trabajo informal alcanza su cifra más alta desde el IV trimestre de 2020. Retrieved 13 April 2024, from CIP- Cámara de Industrias y Producción website: <https://www.cip.org.ec/2023/05/02/el-trabajo-informal-alcanza-su-cifra-mas-alta-desde-el-iv-trimestre-de-2020/>
2. Desempleo en Ecuador alcanza 5,4% en enero en medio de pandemia | Spanish.xinhuanet.com. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2024, from https://spanish.news.cn/2022-02/23/c_1310484916.htm
3. ¿Quién paga por los cuidados? (2021, January 9). Retrieved 28 April 2024, from ArcGIS StoryMaps website: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/dee4686ca729477184fa7301ef5a9192>
4. Juego de mesa Trampas de la informalidad. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2024, from UNDP website: <https://www.undp.org/es/ecuador/publicaciones/juego-de-mesa-trampas-de-la-informalidad>
5. BID | Ecuador promoverá la reactivación económica con apoyo de una garantía del BID. (n.d.). Retrieved 23 April 2024, from <https://www.iadb.org/es/noticias/ecuador-promovera-la-reactivacion-economica-con-apoyo-de-una-garantia-del-bid>
6. INEC. (2023). Encuesta Nacional de Empleo, Desempleo y Subempleo 2023 (ENEMDU). Indicadores de Pobreza y Desigualdad.

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

7. Jaramillo, D. (2024). Cafe' con David Jaramillo. Retrieved 4 April 2024, from Café con David Jaramillo website: <http://www.cafecondavidjaramillo.com/blog/>
8. Las ofertas ilegales han aumentado hasta un 80% en el sector inmobiliario. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2024, from <https://www.lahora.com.ec/pais/informalidad-estafas-sector-inmobiliario/>
9. Ecuador's GDP per capita will recover sooner than expected, says the IMF. (2022, July 27). Ecuador Times. Retrieved from <https://www.ecuadortimes.net/ecuadors-gdp-per-capita-will-recover-sooner-than-expected-says-the-imf/>
10. Iturralde, P. J. (2020, November 19). Ecuador, Covid-19 and Debt. Retrieved 26 April 2024, from Eurodad website: https://www.eurodad.org/ecuador_covid19_and_debt
11. WIEGO. (n.d.). Informality and Illegality: Unpacking the Relationship.
12. Winter, B., & Aalbers, G. (2024). The Capacity to Combat Corruption (CCC) Index Assessing Latin America's ability to detect, punish and prevent corruption. Retrieved from <https://www.controlrisks.com/campaigns/the-capacity-to-combat-corruption-index/thank-you>
13. Constante, S. (2014). Ecuador sumará 7.000 millones de dólares a su deuda con China | Economía | EL PAÍS. El País. Retrieved from https://elpais.com/economia/2014/04/11/actualidad/1397232571_064840.html
14. EcuadorTimes.net | Breaking News, Ecuador News, World, Sports, Entertainment » Informal employment figures continue to rise in Ecuador. (2023). Ecuador Times. Retrieved from <https://www.ecuadortimes.net/informal-employment-figures-continue-to-rise-in-ecuador/>
15. El empleo informal aumentó en julio de 2023, según datos del INEC. (n.d.). Retrieved 13 April 2024, from Primicias website: <https://www.primicias.ec/noticias/economia/empleo-informal-desempleo-ecuador/>
16. Rodríguez, A. (2020). How Quito's urban and peri-urban agriculture contributes to the COVID-19 response | Food for the cities programme. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from FAO.org website: <https://www.fao.org/in-action/food-for-cities-programme/news/detail/en/c/1274823/>
17. Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos. (2024). Índice de Nivel de la Actividad Registrada. Retrieved 13 April 2024, from Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos website: <https://www.ecuadorencifras.gob.ec/indice-de-nivel-de-la-actividad-registrada/>
18. Ecuador EC: Informal Employment: Male: % of Total Non-Agricultural Employment | Economic Indicators | CEIC. (n.d.). Retrieved 13 April 2024, from <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/ecuador/employment-and-unemployment/ec-informal-employment-male--of-total-nonagricultural-employment>
19. Oliveru, M. L., Lupica, C., & La Valley, A. (2023, June 2). Mujer profesional en una oficina, Ley de Economía Violeta en Ecuador: Un instrumento para promover más y mejores oportunidades laborales para las mujeres [Banco Interamericano de Desarrollo]. Retrieved from Y si hablamos de igualdad? website: <https://blogs.iadb.org/igualdad/es/ley-violeta-ecuador/>
20. El Nuevo Ecuador. (n.d.). Empresas Fantasmas—Intersri—Servicio de Rentas Internas. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from <https://www.sri.gob.ec/empresas-fantasma>
21. Carvajal, M. J., Zanoni Lopez, W., & Oliveri, M. L. (2023, July 13). Mujeres en el margen: Características del trabajo informal en Ecuador. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from Factor Trabajo website: <https://blogs.iadb.org/trabajo/es/caracteristicas-del-trabajo-informal-en-ecuador/>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

22. Grijalva, A. M. (2020, Agosto 21). Jóvenes en la informalidad y lo que sabemos sobre sus condiciones de trabajo: Parte 1, levantamiento de información | Programa De Las Naciones Unidas Para El Desarrollo. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from PNUD Ecuador website: <https://www.undp.org/es/ecuador/blog/jovenes-en-la-informalidad-y-lo-que-sabemos-sobre-sus-condiciones-de-trabajo-parte-1-levantamiento-de-informacion>
23. Chevalier Naranjo, S. (2023, June 28). Infografía: ¿A cuánto asciende el empleo informal en América Latina? Retrieved 19 April 2024, from Statista Daily Data website: <https://es.statista.com/grafico/24764/nivel-de-informalidad-laboral-en-latinoamerica>
24. Jóvenes e informalidad laboral | Ecuador 2020. (n.d.). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from <https://informalidadjuvenil.org/>
25. Montenegro, J. D. (2023, August 4). La Informalidad Laboral y la Precariedad en Ecuador, un Análisis Crítico. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from Observatorio de la Dolarización website: <https://dolarizacion.org/2023/08/04/la-informalidad-laboral-y-la-precariedad-en-ecuador-un-analisis-critico/>
26. Andrea, E. por: B. E., Cumbios Andy, Chuya Jorge, Ojeda Skarieth y Pita. (2021, January 28). La mitad de emprendimientos cerraron a raíz del COVID-19. Retrieved 27 April 2024, from ArcGIS StoryMaps website: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4431ac7bc2c742d7a3c287ee5b58443c>
27. Reporta Bloomberg. (2023, February 27). La informalidad laboral domina en Ecuador y absorbe al 55% de trabajadores. Retrieved 19 April 2024, from Santa Fe Casa de Valores S.A. website: <https://www.santafevalores.com/index.php/2023/02/27/sfv20230227uno/>
28. Sube el empleo pleno en Ecuador, pero aún hay informalidad. (2023, August 1). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from <https://www.larepublica.ec/blog/2023/07/31/sube-el-empleo-pleno-en-ecuador-pero-aun-hay-informalidad/>
29. La Informalidad laboral en Ecuador y su Nivel de Instrucción—Konsiloj—Consultores. (2023, July 5). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from <https://konsiloj.com/la-informalidad-laboral-en-ecuador-y-su-nivel-de-instruccion/>
30. Sempértégui, B. (2023, January 12). Los desafíos económicos de Ecuador en 2023. Retrieved 23 April 2024, from Conexion PUCE website: <https://conexion.puce.edu.ec/los-desafios-economicos-de-ecuador-en-2023/>
31. Ecuador, the Country that Vanquished the Nightmare Pandemic in 100 Days. (2021). Retrieved 23 April 2024, from World Bank website: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2021/10/18/ecuador-the-country-that-vanquished-the-nightmare-pandemic-in-100-days>
32. Trotman, W. (2020, November 18). Ecuador’s mishandled COVID-19 health crisis has also had serious economic, educational, and emotional impacts | LSE Latin America and Caribbean. Retrieved 23 April 2024, from LSE Latin America and Caribbean blog website: <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/latamcaribbean/2020/11/18/ecuadors-mishandled-covid-19-health-crisis-has-also-had-serious-economic-educational-and-emotional-impacts/>
33. Covid 19 UCE Ecuador—Investigación sobre los impactos del Covid 19. (n.d.). Retrieved 23 April 2024, from Covid-19 UCE website: <https://covid19uce.com/proyecto-de-investigacion-de-uce-sobre-covid19-en-ecuador/>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

34. Altmann, P., Polo, R., King, K., & Maldonado, R. (2021). Verdades e mentiras sobre a COVID-19 no Ecuador: ruptura de conhecimentos e seus efeitos sociais. *Sociedade E Cultura*, 24. <https://doi.org/10.5216/sec.v24.66048>
35. ACTUARIA. (2023, March 7). El empleo informal ha crecido en el Ecuador. Retrieved 26 April 2024, from ACTUARIA website: <https://actuarial.com.ec/es/el-empleo-informal-ha-crecido-en-el-ecuador-pero-no-la-poblacion-afiliada-al-iess/>
36. Avila, B. (2021, May 27). Impacto del Covid en la Economía ecuatoriana. Retrieved 23 April 2024, from Experiencia global con enfoque en cada país. website: <https://ecovis.com.ec/impacto-del-covid-en-la-economia-ecuatoriana/>
37. Jara, M. (2022, 22 diciembre). El empleo adecuado mejoró en noviembre de 2022 en Ecuador. *El Comercio*. <https://www.elcomercio.com/actualidad/negocios/empleo-adecuado-noviembre-2022-ecuador-cifras.html>
38. Guerrero, A. F., Alex G. Acosta, María Fernanda Tandazo y Anthony. (2021, January 9). Lo que los jóvenes vivimos. Retrieved 28 April 2024, from ArcGIS StoryMaps website: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/66fcc09403c748218708de2e1a8f121a>
39. Ruiz, C. F., Luisa Arellano, Gustavo, Allison Gutiérrez, Eduardo. (2021, January 9). Pérdida de la calidad del empleo joven en la ciudad de Quito. Retrieved 27 April 2024, from ArcGIS StoryMaps website: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/6728cf096231430da01eb2d411faa678>
40. Blog—¿Cómo afectó el terremoto y la pandemia al empleo en Manabí? (n.d.). Retrieved 23 April 2024, from <https://grupofaro.org/empleo-en-manabi/>
41. El inédito y cuestionado plan de emergencia económica de Ecuador contra la crisis del coronavirus. (n.d.). *BBC News Mundo*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/mundo/noticias-52275464>
42. Noticias de América- Ecuador: Una crisis económica agravada por la covid, gran desafío del próximo gobierno. (2021, February 4). Retrieved 23 April 2024, from RFI website: <https://www.rfi.fr/es/programas/noticias-de-am%C3%A9rica/20210204-ecuador-una-crisis-econ%C3%B3mica-agravada-por-la-covid-gran-desaf%C3%ADo-del-pr%C3%B3ximo-gobierno>
43. Chejín, S. R. (2020, March 15). El impacto del covid-19 en la economía del Ecuador. Retrieved 23 April 2024, from GK website: <https://gk.city/2020/03/15/impacto-economico-coronavirus-ecuador/>
44. La informalidad ronda el 56% en los 4 principales sectores económicos. (2022). Retrieved 24 April 2024, from <https://www.lahora.com.ec/pais/informalidad-sectores-economicos-empleo-economia/>
45. Canelos, R. (2022, May 5). Un nuevo bloqueo al desarrollo. Retrieved 24 April 2024, from *El Telégrafo* website: <https://www.eltelegrafo.com.ec/noticias/articulas/15/nuevo-bloqueo-desarrollo>
46. New Report: Informal Economy and Culture in the Global South. (n.d.). Retrieved 26 April 2024, from *British Council | Creative Economy* website: <https://creativeeconomy.britishcouncil.org/blog/21/07/27/informal-economy-blog-post/>
47. UTPL. (2020). COVID-19 en Ecuador: Potenciales impactos en la pobreza | Blog. Retrieved 26 April 2024, from <https://noticias.utpl.edu.ec/covid-19-en-ecuador-potenciales-impactos-en-la-pobreza>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

48. UNU WIDER: UNU-WIDER ongoing work on the effect of COVID-19 on the economies, states, and societies of the Global South. (n.d.). Retrieved 26 April 2024, from <http://www.wider.unu.edu/article/unu-wider-ongoing-work-effect-covid-19-economies-states-and-societies-global-south>

49. Reid, T. (2024, March 18). UNU-WIDER: Blog : Research in focus – country profiles: Indonesia and Ecuador. Retrieved 26 April 2024, from UNU WIDER website: <http://www.wider.unu.edu/publication/research-focus-country-profiles-indonesia-and-ecuador>

50. UNU WIDER: ECUAMOD- simulating tax and benefit policies for development in Ecuador. (n.d.). Retrieved 27 April 2024, from <http://www.wider.unu.edu/about/ecuamod-simulating-tax-and-benefit-policies-development-ecuador>

Grey Literature

1. Arias, D. (2018). Financial inclusion policy in Ecuador: Role of the Central Bank towards economic growth and job creation. In Financial inclusion policy in Ecuador: Role of the Central Bank towards economic growth and job creation. Geneva: ILO.

4. CountryWatch—Country Review United States. (n.d.). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from <https://www.countrywatch.com/intelligence/countryreviews?countryid=54>

5. Duri, J. (2020). The relationship between corruption, gender and human rights in Ecuador. U4 Anti-Corruption Resource Centre.

6. ECLAC. (2022). Economic Survey of Latin America and the Caribbean—Ecuador.

7. OIT. (2020). 200 días de acción: La respuesta de la ILO antes la crisis del covid en los países andinos.

8. Ulloa, A. A. (2021). Segregación socio espacial en Cumbayá-Distrito Metropolitano de Quito. *revistapuce*, (112). Retrieved from <https://www.revistapuce.edu.ec/index.php/revpuce/article/view/355>

9. FAO. (2023). Mapping territorial markets in Ecuador. (No. Second Edition). Rome. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb9436en>

10. FDC. (2022). Barómetro de la Corrupción Ecuador 2022 | Ciudadanía y Desarrollo. Retrieved 3 January 2024, from <https://www.ciudadaniaydesarrollo.org/publicaciones/barometrocorrupcionecuador2022/> Foreign Trade Barriers. (n.d.). Trade summary.

11. Hassan, M., & Schneider, F. (2016). Size and Development of the Shadow Economies of 157 Countries Worldwide: Updated and New Measures from 1999 to 2013 (Discussion Paper No. 10281). Germany.

12. IFAD. (2023, June 11). Ecuador country facts. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/ecuador>

13. IWGIA. (2023). The Indigenous World 2023: Ecuador—IWGIA- International Work Group for Indigenous Affairs. Retrieved 2 October 2023, from <https://www.iwgia.org/en/ecuador/5087-iw-2023-ecuador.html>

14. OECD. (2021). Public Integrity in Ecuador: Towards a National Integrity System. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9623672c-en>

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

15. Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos. (2024). Registro de Empleo en la Seguridad Social. Retrieved 13 April 2024, from <https://www.ecuadorencifras.gob.ec/registro-empleo-seguridad-social/>
16. Ruiz Maldonado, L. E. (2015). Pueblos y nacionalidades indígenas del Ecuador: De la reivindicación al protagonismo político.
17. Vuletin, G. (2008, April 1). Measuring the Informal Economy in Latin America and the Caribbean [SSRN Scholarly Paper]. Rochester, NY. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1153724>
18. Simon, R., & Aalbers, G. (2020). The 2020 Capacity to Combat Corruption Index AS/COA. Retrieved 7 February 2024, from <https://www.as-coa.org/articles/2020-capacity-combat-corruption-index>
19. Transparency International. (2023). Ecuador. Retrieved 12 October 2023, from Transparency.org website: <https://www.transparency.org/en/countries/ecuador>
20. ILO. (2018). Women and men in the informal economy: A statistical picture (third edition). Geneva.
21. Winter, B., & Aalbers, G. (2024). The Capacity to Combat Corruption (CCC) Index Assessing Latin America's ability to detect, punish and prevent corruption. Retrieved from <https://www.controlrisks.com/campaigns/the-capacity-to-combat-corruption-index/thank-you>
22. World Bank. (2018). Project Information Document/Integrated Safeguards Data Sheet (PID/ISDS).Ecuador Forest Investment Program (P167752)
23. Joint SDG Fund. (2020). Portfolio on integrated social protection and LNOB. Country: Ecuador [Annual Progress Report].
24. UNDP Ecuador Accelerator Lab. (n.d.). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from UNDP website: <https://www.undp.org/acceleratorlabs/undp-ecuador-accelerator-lab>
25. Fiorentini, M. (ESP). (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on informal workers. FAO.
26. Statistics on the informal economy. (n.d.). Retrieved 19 April 2024, from ILOSTAT website: <https://ilostat.ilo.org/topics/informality/>
27. La Porta, R., & Shleifer, A. (2008). The unofficial economy and economic development. National Bureau of Economic Research, (Working Paper 14520). Retrieved from <http://www.nber.org/papers/w14520>
28. Acevedo, J., Benabentos, L., & Rodriguez, A. (2020). IFRC COVID-19 Emergency Decree Pro Bono Research: Republic of Ecuador. White and Case.
29. Medina, L., & Deléchat, C. C. (2021). La fuerza laboral informal en el mundo. Prioridades para un crecimiento inclusivo (p. 19). Washington, DC: FMI.
30. OECD. (2018). Latin America and Caribbean Competition Forum—Session I: Informal Economy in Latin America and the Caribbean: Implications for Competition Policy. (DAF/COMP/LACF(2018)4).
31. Lazarte, C. (n.d.). Inclusión financiera de las mujeres. Claves para una recuperación transformadora de la economía post COVID-19 en América Latina y el Caribe. Retrieved 23 April 2024, from ONU Mujeres – América Latina y el Caribe website: <https://lac.unwomen.org/es/digital-library/publications/2022/12/inclusion-financiera-de-las->

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

mujeres-claves-para-una-recuperacion-transformadora-de-la-economia-de-la-economia-post-covid-en-america-latina

32. ILO. (2020). COVID-19 and the impact on agriculture and food security. Geneva.
33. Correa-Quezada, R., Izquierdo-Montoya, L., & García-Vélez, M. D. (2020). Impacto del COVID-19 en Ecuador. Departamento de Economía Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja.
34. Castro, L., & Fernández, J. (2020). Un país conectado a un respirador: Ecuador y la crisis provocada por el COVID-19. Retrieved from <http://repositorio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/handle/10469/17106>
35. Molina Vera, A., Rivadeneira Alava, A., & Rosero Moncayo, J. (2018). Actualización metodológica: El empleo en el sector informal [Documento metodológico de la Encuesta de Empleo, Desempleo y Subempleo (ENEMDU)].
36. Córdova, C. L. V., Quinaucho, B. F. L., Espinoza, A. L. B., & Villavicencio, V. M. (2020). Proyecto elaborado en el marco de la escuela de datos datea, edición jóvenes e informalidad laboral [DATEA]. Quito.
37. Bárcena, A. (2020). ALC ante la crisis del COVID-19: Cómo debe ser la reactivación. *Pensamiento iberoamericano*, (9 (3ª ÉPOCA / 01 / 2020)), 12–23.
38. Blanco, A. (2021). América Latina post COVID-19: Riesgos y oportunidades del nuevo ciclo económico—Elcano [Estudios internacionales y estratégicos]. Real Instituto el Cano. http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/portal/rielcano_es/contenido?WCM_GLOBAL_CONTEXT=/elcano/elcano_es/zonas_es/ari65-2021-blanco-america-latina-post-covid-19-riesgos-y-oportunidades-nuevo-ciclo-economico
39. Vaca, J. (2021). Financial mechanisms for innovative social and solidarity economy ecosystems: The case of Ecuador. Geneva: ILO
40. OECD. (2020). OECD Employment Outlook 2020: Worker Security and the COVID-19 Crisis | OECD iLibrary. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1686c758-en>.
41. Zanuto Andrade Santos, H. C., & Fraga, G. J. (2020). Corrupción, estructura productiva y desarrollo económico en los países en desarrollo (No. 130).
42. Uquillas, C. A. (2007). El outsourcing en el Ecuador. Observatorio de La Economía Latinoamericana. Retrieved from <https://www.eumed.net/cursecon/ecolat/ec/2007/cau-outsourcing.htm>
43. Medina, L., & Schneider, F. (2018). Shadow Economies Around the World: What did we learn around the last 20 years? (No. WP/18/17). IMF.
44. Tributaria, R., & Romero, V. (2018). Las brechas de recaudación tributaria del impuesto al valor agregado. Observatorio de la Economía Latinoamericana, (junio). Retrieved from <https://www.eumed.net/rev/oel/2018/06/recaudacion-tributaria-ecuador.html>
45. Ernst, C., & Leung, V. (2023). Trade and informality: Transition to formality and decent work. In *Integrating trade and decent work* (Vol. 1, pp. 277–310). Geneva: ILO.
46. Ohnsorge, F., & Yu, S. (2022). *The Long Shadow of Informality: Challenges and Policies*. Washington, DC: World Bank Group.
47. Handeland, C., & Gómez Ramírez, E. (2021). *The informal economy and coronavirus in Latin America*. European Parliamentary Research Service.

EC/MSCA-DN Grant Agreement ID 101073394

48. Velasco Abad, M., & Hurtado Caicedo, F. X. (2020). La pandemia en Ecuador. Desigualdades, impactos y desafíos. Observatorio Social del Ecuador y FES-Ildis.

49. Tenorio-Rosero, M. L., Veintimilla-Almeida, D. G., & Reyes-Herrera, M. A. (2021). The COVID-19 economic crisis in Ecuador: Implications and projections for mental health and safety. *Revista Investigacion y Desarrollo*, 13, 88–102. Universidad tecnica de Ambato. Retrieved from Universidad tecnica de Ambato.

50. Avilez, M., Vanessa, K., Robalino, M., Estefania, N., Valencia, C., & Rodrigo, M. (2021). Impacto generado por la pandemia del COVID-19 en la población económicamente activa (Carrera de Ingeniería Estadística). Universidad Central del Ecuador, Quito.